

Assessment of the effectiveness of methods for reducing soil salinization based on experimental data for Uzbekistan

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Abstract. The article briefly analyzes foreign approaches to regulating the salt regime of soils and compares them with leaching methods used in Uzbekistan. Based on experimental data from the authors' field studies, a comparison was made of the effectiveness of check leaching and alternative methods of soil desalinization for the conditions of Uzbekistan. The purpose of this study is to find a method for amelioration of saline soils with economical use of water, taking into account the scarcity of water resources. The materials can serve as a guide for choosing technology for regulating the salt regime of the kidney in various conditions and situations.

1 Introduction

Water conservation in irrigated agriculture in Central Asia and Uzbekistan is relevant both now and in the future. In Uzbekistan, this is primarily due to the limited availability of its own water resources and population growth. With climate change, due to rising temperatures, glaciers are melting, and, accordingly, the flow of transboundary rivers is changing. According to expert forecasts, it is predicted that in 2030-2050 the air temperature in the Central Asian region may increase by another 1.5-3°C. In accordance with this, according to calculations until 2050, a decrease in water resources is expected: in the Syrdarya basin - by 5-10%, in the Amu Darya basin - by 10-15%. [1]. According to forecasts, by 2030, the water shortage in our country could reach 15 billion cubic meters. The most optimal solution to the problem of water shortage is its conservation and rational use. [1].

The need to find means, technologies and measures for the economical use of water concerns all sectors of the economy. But it is most important to introduce technologies for economical use of water in irrigated agriculture, which consumes 90% of Uzbekistan's water resources, despite the fact that only 12% of the used volumes of water are formed within the borders of the republic.

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The Concept for the Development of Water Resources of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2020-2030 sets the task of introducing water-saving technologies on at least 50% of the country's 4.3 million hectares of irrigated land [concept].

In addition to irrigation, 90% of the water resources used include water costs for regulating the salt regime of soils (reclamation), which in areas of saline lands can reach up to 25% of water intake [2].

Salinization on irrigated lands of Uzbekistan is widespread over 45% of the territory (data from the Ministry of Water Resources). Every year in the winter-spring period, farmers leach saline lands using various technologies to reduce soil salinity and create conditions for sowing crops. This requires an average of 3-4 thousand m³/ha of water. In addition, for successful leaching of lands with moderate and strong salinity in the winter-spring period, restoration of drainage systems is required. The need to improve soil desalinization technology is part of measures for the rational use of water resources, taking into account their likely shortage in the present and future.

This article briefly describes international approaches to regulating the salt regime of soils, and also presents the results of experimental work on soil desalinization carried out by the authors.

1.1 Review of foreign approaches to maintaining the water-salt regime of soils

In foreign literature, much attention is paid to salinity management during crop irrigation. At the same time, the main factor is often the quality of irrigation water, and regulation of the salt regime is considered as the calculation and implementation of the leaching fraction of water supply, in excess of the needs of plants of a certain crop (LF-Leaching fraction) during vegetation irrigation [3-10]. In this case, drainage must be ensured. The same sources, in order to successfully leach the soil from salts, mention the importance of the rate of water infiltration into the soil, which should not be too low or too high. Also, as an option, the possibility of leaching the soil with precipitation [8-10] and the advisability of special loosening of the soil to enhance infiltration are mentioned. Chemical amelioration, including the use of acids, is also described. [11].

The paper [10] notes "that there are several shortcomings in the LR (Leaching requirement) concept as proposed using steady-state analysis. The LR concept is based on achieving maximum output. Maximum yield may not be economically optimal. This is especially true when only saline waters are available and the potential maximum yield is not possible." Advances in irrigation technology, such as microirrigation and sprinkler systems, make it possible to irrigate with very low leaching fraction (LF) values. However, irrigation at a very low leaching rate (LF) can lead to soil salinization and reduced crop yields. This is confirmed by studies of controlled watering of cucumbers using drip irrigation in greenhouses with mineralized water.

Regardless of the frequency of irrigation, when adding water 25% more than is required to restore the value of evapotranspiration and prevent an increase in soil salinity, the use of drip irrigation was ineffective [12]. In addition, the author of the study, citing Hoorn [13], explains that salt leaching in clay soils is less effective than in sandy soils due to the presence of preferential paths and greater soil dispersion. Therefore, relatively large volumes of water pass through the soil layer without mixing with soil water. The author [12] also points out that the presence of a compacted layer at a depth of 0.2 m, due to repeated long-term plowing, reduces the water permeability of the soil and contributes to the formation of a shallow root system, as well as a decrease in the efficiency of leaching.

The influence of groundwater and the provision of drainage is considered in the study [14], which the authors carried out on the basis of qualitative and quantitative analysis and

statistical processing of stochastic (expert) data, using a diagram, the relationship between the consequences of problems and their causes. Based on this analysis, the following list of risks was compiled:

- The effect of rising groundwater levels on increasing soil salinity.
- The influence of the irrigation system on soil salinity.
- The effect of poor drainage system on soil salinity.

At the same time, doubt arises about the possibility of implementing a uniform leaching regime across the field in practice, both when irrigating in furrows and when drip irrigation is used on compacted clay soils. In addition, many models do not take into account the content of salts already present in the soil, and take into account the estimated amount of salts supplied with mineralized water used for irrigation. To model processes using LF theory, it is necessary to understand under what boundary conditions such a model works? What should be the acceptable soil filtration parameters for this model to “work” in accordance with the theory of processes?

The main assumption made in estimating LR is that irrigation water can easily infiltrate and move through the soil, creating the design drainage required for leaching [14]. Speaking about the use of low-quality water, the author [14] notes the requirements of three changes compared to standard irrigation practices: (1) selection of salt-tolerant crops; (2) improving water management and, in some cases, introducing advanced irrigation technologies; and (3) maintaining soil physicochemical properties to ensure soil looseness and sufficient permeability to meet crop water and leaching (LR) requirements. [14]. In our opinion, with the exception of (1), this applies to any management of saline soils - to the regulation of soil salinity within acceptable limits for plants. The author also further emphasizes, “The key to salinity control and irrigation sustainability is leaching, that is, a net downward flow, moving soil water and salts through the root zone.

The same paper provides examples of farm experiences where water caused problems with infiltration rates and soil density, and the methods used to solve these problems. [14].

Soil washing by flooding, in the approach adopted by FAO scientists, is recommended only for land development [3]. Typical methods used during the development phases include leveling the land to a specified slope, establishing adequate drainage (closed or open drains), deep plowing or loosening to physically change the soil profile, and leaching to reduce excessive salinity.

According to the author’s recommendations, it is advisable to carry out ameliorative flushing with a layer of water (flooding) only if the salinity of the upper root zone is much higher than E_{Ce} , 10–12 dS/m. This FAO document [3] expresses the advantage of water entering unsaturated soil. This refers to the intermittency of flooding (tacts) or the application of sprinkling. “Efficiency increases if the percolating water moves more slowly (unsaturated flow) and is occasionally allowed to drain, as occurs in intermittent leaching. With continuous flooding, most of the leaching water passes through the larger soil pores and bypasses the smaller pores. Therefore, salts trapped in these smaller pores are removed at a slower rate per unit of water applied. Typically, with continuous flooding, 70–80 percent of the soluble salts originally present will be removed by a layer of water equal to the layer of soil being washed. “Efficiency increases if the percolating water moves more slowly (unsaturated flow) and is occasionally allowed to drain, as occurs in intermittent leaching. With continuous flooding, most of the leaching water passes through the larger soil pores and bypasses the smaller pores. Therefore, salts trapped in these smaller pores are removed at a slower rate per unit of water applied. Typically, with continuous flooding, 70–80 percent of the soluble salts originally present will be removed by a layer of water equal to the layer of soil being leached.

Sprinklers deliver water at a relatively slow rate and are very effective at leaching salts. When using sprinklers or intermittent flooding, about 80 to 90 percent of the salts originally

present in the soil will be removed with a water supply equal to the soil being restored, but leaching will take longer to complete” [3 (Section 2.4.6)]. From the above review materials, it is clear that the best regulation of the salt regime depends on a number of conditions, such as the availability of water and its quality, as well as soil properties, especially infiltration, which in turn is determined by the genetic properties of the rocks, as well as the chemical composition of salts.

In Uzbekistan, regulation of the soil salt regime by farmers is similar to that set out in the publication [16], which assesses the effectiveness of various options for regulating the soil salt regime with different water supply technologies:

- During the non-growing season (winter-spring) period, by flooding checks and furrows.
- During the period of cotton irrigation.
- With the use of atmospheric precipitation for leaching of salts, with increased infiltration by loosening soils and chemical exposure, with the help of drugs.

From a brief review of foreign sources, useful conclusions can be drawn regarding the current state of water resources and the properties of saline lands (lack of water, lack of drainage, insufficient soil infiltration, close location of groundwater), the following conclusions can be drawn:

- The leaching share during irrigation is best ensured by surface irrigation (along furrows, along strips), but it is also impossible to take into account the implementation of the leaching share (irrigation rate), including due to the uneven distribution of soil moisture along the length of the field [16].
- The maximum yield may not be economically optimal, therefore all leaching models take into account the possibly achievable (given) limit of soil desalinization, while in domestic approaches the desalination of soils to the degree of “non-saline” was considered;
- Leaching by checks, with a layer of water, is recommended only when developing land when water is supplied in cycles in clay soils, while in local approaches such leaching technology was recommended annually in the autumn-winter-spring period of the year;
- In foreign studies, with all technologies for leaching saline soils, the importance of optimal soil infiltration is mentioned, which in local practice is taken into account only indirectly (mechanical composition, salt release index, etc.).
- From leaching experiments, it has been noticed and proven that rinsing clay soils with a layer of water in checks often does not produce an effect: the soil swells, floats, and water filtration decreases [19.]. Accordingly, the leaching efficiency decreases. Based on this, it should probably be recognized that leaching during the period before the growing season (in the form of moisture recharging by cycles) and regulating the salt regime during the growing season, during the irrigation period, seems to be a reasonable solution;
- Published sources provide many useful theoretical justifications and models of salt leaching processes. At the same time, the literature does not sufficiently reflect the results of experimental studies on leaching of saline soils, confirming these hypotheses, both when leaching with a layer of water and using a leaching fraction during the growing season. Testing the hypotheses set out in the developed models of the processes of leaching of saline soils is a task for local conditions.

In this aspect, the research material on land leaching, obtained by the authors in the field, seems important and scientifically significant.

2 Assessment and comparison of the effectiveness of check leaching with alternative methods of soil desalinization for the conditions of Uzbekistan

In works [15-18], we examined the effectiveness of leaching saline lands using various technologies. As a result of the study [15], it was revealed that to desalinize soil from the degree of strong salinity to weak, approximately 6000 m³/ha of water will be required. Also, based on an analysis of comparison of experimental data, it was concluded that when there is a shortage of water on soils of moderate salinity, it is advisable to carry out leaching along furrows, both from an economic and environmental point of view.

This article also analyzes the results of experimental leaching and a number of innovative water-saving technologies for reclamation of saline lands, alternative to check leaching, studied by the authors. The data experiments carried out were compared with the results of leaching by checks against the background of ensured drainage. Soil desalinization technologies are considered from the point of view of saving water resources and increasing yields, depending on the amount of leached salts and the achieved level of soil desalinization (Table 1).

Table 1 also shows the results of experiments in 2023 on experimental testing of hypotheses: about soil desalinization by precipitation and about leaching along furrows, as an alternative to leaching along checks on soils with unfavorable properties.

The article also uses materials on regulating the salt regime of an irrigated field during the growing season by improving the distribution of water across the field [17], using Biosolvent [18], as well as previously unpublished materials from the authors on studying the effectiveness of furrow leaching in the Syrdarya region.

From the table below, conclusions are drawn about the effectiveness of various technologies, including furrow leaching. From the table below, conclusions are drawn about the effectiveness of various technologies, including furrow leaching. Furrow leaching is not a completely new technology. Many farmers carry out leaching along the furrows, combining it with moisture recharging. In this study, the goal was to use furrow leaching as an alternative by checks leaching in conditions of low salinity, limited water, and lack of drainage. To enhance the effect of leaching along the furrows in the experimental variants, the use of deep loosening and the use of Biosolvent were considered.

Experiments on furrow leaching 2023.

3 Materials and methods

The experiment was carried out in 4 variants (Figure 1).

Options for furrow leaching experience:

- K-Control - on the no-lose soil.
- KB - on no-lose soil, with furrows sprayed with Biosolvent before water supply (10% solution, 5 liters of the product per 1 ha).
- R-on pre-loosened soil to a depth of 70 cm.
- RB - on loose soil, with spraying the furrows with Biosolvent before adding water (10% solution, 5 liters of the product per 1 ha).

Before the start of leaching, the following field work and research was carried out on the fields:

- Plowing, making blunt furrows, cutting ditches and dams (rollers). The furrow length was 100 m in all experimental variants.
- Two soil sections were laid and the volumetric mass of the soil was determined (using the cutting ring method).

- Soil infiltration was determined by Nesterov's method. The level and salinity of groundwater were measured.
- Measurement of water flow for flushing is carried out using a Cipoletti weir.
- Soil sampling was carried out before and after leaching at observation points (Figure 1) in horizons of 0-30, 30-70 cm. ECe analyzes were performed on all soil samples before and after leaching. In samples located in the middle of the cross section, analyzes were performed for pH, EC, Dense residue, HCO₃, Cl⁻, SO₄²⁻, Ca., Mg., Na⁺, K⁺. Computer processing of the data was carried out, graphs were constructed, on the basis of which the leaching efficiency was compared.

Fig. 1. Experience scheme.

For detailed monitoring by all options, a cross-section was laid out including the following points:

- K2, K5, K8 – control option for non-loose soil.
- KB2, KB5, KB8 - option without loosening the soil using Biosolvent.
- P2, P5, P8 – option with soil loosening.
- RB2, RB5, RB8 – option with soil loosening + use of Biosolvent.

According to the results of field studies of soils, volumetric mass 1.7 g/cm³, infiltration, water into the soil 0.01 mm/min, soil mechanical composition medium loam.

4 Results and Discussion

Table 1 shows the results of soil washing in the experimental variants.

Table 1 shows the change in soil salinity under the influence of leaching according to ECe in the experimental variants (according to the average data of all observation points in each experimental variant in a layer of 30-70 cm). The table shows that conventional leaching (Control-K) with a water supply of 700 m³/ha changed soil salinity by 0.7 dS/m in option K, and in the option with Biosolvent (without loosening the soil, option KB) by 1.2 dS/m, with a water consumption of 850 m³/ha. The ECe ratio in the KB/K variants is 1.7

times. That is, according to these data, the use of Biosolvent on non-loose soil increased the leaching of salts from the soil by 70%.

Table 1. Comparison of the results of leaching along furrows at all observation points (layer 30-70 cm).

Variants	ECe, dS/m				Specific water costs m ³ /ha per 1 dS/m
	March 17	April 12	Difference	In %, to the initial	
K	7.5	6.8	-0.7	-9.6	700/971
КБ	7.6	6.3	-1.2	-16.5	1000/799
P	9.8	9.0	-0.85	-8.7	850/998
РБ	12.9	11.1	-1.7	-13.4	1400/812
Increased leaching of salts and comparison of specific water consumption in options, number of times					
КБ/К	Biosolvent + Control/Control (on a non-loosened background)		1.7		0.82
P/K	Loose soil/non-loose soil		1.2		1.03
РБ/К	Loosening + Biosolvent/Control		2.4		0.84
РБ/P	Loosening + Biosolvent/Loose soil		2		0.81
РБ/БК	Loosening + Biosolvent/ Biosolvent + Control (without loosening)		1.4		1.02

Likewise, in variants with deep loosening. If we compare the leaching of loosened and non-loosened soil - L/K, it turns out that loosening the soil in this experiment increased the removal of salts by 20% (Table 2). Conventional leaching against the background of loosening changed soil salinity (option P, water supply rate 850 m³/ha) by 0.85 dS/m. In the variant with Biosolvent on loose soil (LB variant), the leaching of salts was 1.7 dS/m, with a water supply of 1400 m³/ha. Thus, Biosolvent, due to the background of loosening, increased the leaching of salts by half (or by 100%). If this variant of salt leaching is compared with the Control variant, it is clear that the efficiency of salt leaching with the simultaneous use of both loosening and Biosolvent increases by 2.4 times compared to the control.

Nevertheless, it should be noted that the intensity of salt leaching is greatly influenced by both the initial degree of soil salinity and the amount of water supplied. Thus, despite the insufficient efficiency of the furrow leaching, this experiment was able to identify the effect of loosening and Biosolvent on leaching in unloosened and loosened fields.

On the non-loosened field, Biosolvent increases salt leaching by 70%, on the loosened field – by 100%, and loosening itself increases the leaching efficiency by 20-40%.

The reasons for insufficient furrow leaching are obviously:

- Soil properties: low water infiltration, which was not eliminated when loosening the soil (a similar phenomenon was noted in the work of [19] is explained by the presence of gypsum layers of soil), density more than 1.7 g/cm³, the presence of a carbonate layer.
- Unsatisfactory distribution of water across the field (due to insufficient leveling).
- Insufficient amount of water supplied to the furrows and incomplete saturation of the furrow ridges with moisture, including due to the forced supply of water in one cycle, a long run of water - 100 m (Figure 2).

Under these conditions, it was obviously necessary to carry out leaching by checks, also using deep loosening and Biosolvent. However, based on the amount of toxic salts by cross section (Figures 3 and 4), soil desalination was achieved: in option 5, up to 38% and in option 6, up to 60%.

Fig. 2. Leaching by furrows.

Fig. 3. Changes in the content of toxic salts under the influence of furrow leaching.

The experience of leaching along furrows showed that under the conditions of the study (Mirzaabad district of the Syrdarya region), the greatest influence on the efficiency of leaching is exerted by soil properties: density, water infiltration and initial salinity. The technology of leaching along furrows needs to be improved, with high-quality field planning and water supply in cycles along shorter furrows. Despite the differences in the initial soil salinity in the variants, experience made it possible to quantify the effectiveness of using agro-reclamation techniques (loosening and Biosolvent). To increase the leaching of salts: the use of loosening increases the removal of salts by 20-40%, and the use of Biosolvent by 70-100%.

Table 2 shows the results of a comparison of various soil desalinization technologies (70 cm layer) and an analysis of water savings and potential and actual increases in cotton yields.

All studied technologies for soil desalinization are compared with the basic option “leaching by checks” (1). Data from individual experiments differ in the initial soil salinity, the amount of water and its supply technology, and in the results of soil desalinization. The effectiveness of desalinization measures is assessed by specific water consumption to reduce soil salinization, save irrigation water and increase cotton yield.

Fig. 4. Change in the content of the sum of toxic salts, % to initial (30-70 cm layer).

The table shows that, compared with check leaching, the greatest water savings and yield increases are provided by two technologies “controlling the salt regime during the growing season”: 6-counter irrigation along the furrows and 7-irrigation using Biosolvent. Both of these options provide a favorable salt regime for the soil without spending additional volumes of water for leaching of salts. Counter irrigation ensures uniformity of the salt background and reduces the seasonal accumulation of salts on the field. The use of Biosolvent during vegetation irrigation along furrows creates a leaching irrigation regime, with virtually no additional water consumption, only due to the intensification of the process of leaching of salts. The actual increases in cotton yields in these technologies are, respectively: 36% in counter-irrigation and 22% in the experiment with Biosolvent.

Table 2. Efficiency of water-saving technologies for land reclamation of saline lands in comparison with leaching by checks.

Effectiveness indicators	Leaching by checks (highly and moderately saline soils)		Leaching and other methods of soil desalinization when water is supplied through furrows (medium and slightly saline soils)					Degraded lands inside developed irrigated areas: highly saline and compacted soils	
	Research options								
	Leaching by checks -		Leaching along the furrows combined with moisture charging			Soil desalinization during vegetative irrigation of cotton in furrows		Desalinization by precipitation when loosening the soil in autumn + Biosolvent	
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
	Displacement of salts with a layer of water (basic) [15]	The same, using Biosolvent [16]	Light soils: leaching by facts [scientific report 2023]	Compact soils [scientific report 2023]	Dense soils: loosening + leaching [scientific report 2023]	Counter irrigation on small slopes [17]	Cotton irrigation + Biosolvent [16]	1 year (302 mm precipitation) [2]	2nd year (174 mm precipitation) [scientific report 2023]
Decrease in soil salinity E _{Ce} (dS/m) in the soil layer 0-70 cm	4.3 (8.3-4.0)	3.0 (8.5-5.5)	3.3 (5.1-1.7)	1.7 (7.3-5.6)	2.8 (11.2-8.2)	0.1 (10.2-10.3) increase during the growing season, 2 half of the field	2.3 (7.4-5.1) due to the leaching regime	6.6 (11.9-5.3)	3.9 (9.0-5.1)
Consumption of irrigation water for soil desalinization, thousand m ³ /ha	4.4	2.0	1.75	0.7	1.4	0 (vegetative irrigation)	0 (vegetative irrigation)	0	0
The same, specific water consumption decrease 1 dS/m salinity, m ³ /ha	1029	667	530	412	500	0	0	0	0
Irrigation water savings, % (by specific water consumption)	0	35	48	60	51	100%	100%	100%	100%
Yield increase, % potential (fact)	27	13	14	11	19	36	22	41	24

The great prospect of water saving is confirmed by two-year studies on the possibility of soil desalination by precipitation, with deep loosening of soils and the use of Biosolvent (8, 9). Depending on the amount of precipitation, soil desalination was: 6.6 dS/m at 302 mm of precipitation and 3.9 dS/m at 174 mm (Table 2).

It was noticed that on the same site in the Mirzaabad district of the Syrdarya region, with an initial salinity of 11, 9 and 11.2 dS/m, the use of loosening and Biosolvent, the efficiency of slow desalination of soil by precipitation was higher, than with forced water supply when leaching along furrows (Table 2). Therefore, the low-cost technology of using precipitation for soil desalination is promising.

5 Conclusion

A comparison of leaching by checks and furrows allows us to draw the following conclusion:

- If there is enough water and drainage of rinsing water is ensured, then rinsing highly saline soils by checks is preferable (option 1).
- If there is not enough water, then due to enhanced leaching of salts, water supply can be reduced by approximately 30%, but at the same time, soil desalinization will be less, as will the increase in yield (option-2).
- If the soils are light in texture, then leaching along the furrows in 2 steps with alternating furrows can provide water savings of 48% (option-3) increase in yield of 14% due to the tolerance of cotton to salts.
- Leaching dense, medium-saline soils along furrows, without loosening and other measures (option 5), was not effective enough. A reduction in soil salinity was achieved from 7.3 to 5.6 dS/m (by 1.7 dS/m), with low irrigation water consumption - 700 m³/ha. Water savings -60%, with a small increase in cotton yield -11%. Under these conditions, it is obviously advisable to improve the salt release of soils by enhancing the filtration properties of the soil - using deep loosening and increasing the leaching of salts with Biosolvent.
- The use of deep loosening and Biosolvent on soils with low salt release (the same conditions as in the experiment - option-5) turned out to be insufficiently effective in desalinizing the soil in option-6 (Table 2). With a water supply of 1400 m³/ha, soil salinity decreased by 2.8 (from 11.2 to 8.2 dS/m.). Reasons: high initial degree of soil salinity and also “rolling” of water along the furrow bed (when checking the effect of loosening on water infiltration, the changes were insignificant). The option showed water savings of -51%, but a small potential increase in cotton yield of -19%.
- The above materials can serve as a guide for choosing a technology for regulating the salt regime of the soil in various conditions and situations, taking into account the degree of soil salinity, lack of water, soil compaction, lack of drainage, etc.
- When making a decision on soil desalinization technology, it is very important to have information about the initial salinity of the soil, as well as its properties (density and water infiltration).

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